

WHY ISN'T MODULAR CONSTRUCTION WIDELY USED IN HIGH-RISE BUILDINGS?

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ABSTRACT

The onset of urbanization has brought about the rapid growth of population in metropolitan cities. Due to the increasing population density, the demand for housing has also increased.

The construction of housing using conventional methods is a time-consuming process which has a negative impact on the environment and is costly. The high cost of land in these areas only adds to this issue. As a result, slums with overcrowded and unhygienic living conditions are very commonly seen in these urban cities. The construction of high-rise mass housing to rehabilitate the people in a faster and cheaper way is essential to raise their living standards.

This paper discusses modular construction technology as a means to provide the population with masshousing which is low cost, sustainable, and durable high-rise structures with minimum construction waste and pollution. Further, the challenges faced by the architects while designing these structures and residents after its occupation are also taken into consideration.

The aim of this research is to highlight modular construction as a more efficient alternative to conventional construction and the significance of introducing these new technologies in the construction of mass housing.

Key words: Modular, High Rise, Residential, Volumetric.

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INTRODUCTION

A modular building is a prefabricated building that consists of repetitive units called modules. These modules are room sized volumetric units that are constructed off site, under controlled conditions in factories using the same building materials and designed to the same codes and standards as conventionally built facilities. These modules are then installed on site according to the design as loadbearing structures.

The designs created using combination of these modules with steel or concrete frames increases the range of design opportunities, particularly for mixed-use commercial and residential buildings. The primary advantages of modular structures are:

- speed of construction and installation on site,
- reduced material wastage and
- improved quality and accuracy. [1]

A module is 25 to 30 m. sq. in floor area and is often used for single person accommodation. Two modules are suitable for a unit occupied by two people (with one bedroom) and three or four modules are suitable for family-sized units. [2]

The kitchens and bathrooms are arranged next to the corridor or other accessible space so that service connections and maintenance can be carried out relatively easily. The design of high-rise modular buildings is strongly influenced by structural, fire and services requirements. From a design viewpoint, two generic floor plans may be considered for the spatial relationship of the modules around a stabilizing concrete core:

- A cluster of modules, which are accessed from the core or from lobbies next to the core, as illustrated in Fig. 1.
- A corridor arrangement of modules, in which the modules are accessed from corridors either side of the core, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Typical layout of rooms clustered around a core

Fig. 2. Typical corridor arrangement of modules

HISTORY OF MODULAR CONSTRUCTION

ORIGINS

The origins of modular buildings date back to the 1600s. One of the first reported modular homes was brought to life by a colonial American fisherman who had recently moved from England and wanted a home built with trusted English construction methods.

In the 1800s, During the California Gold Rush, mining towns boomed, and more than 500 preassembled homes were built in factories in New York and then shipped across the country to California. [3]

20TH CENTURY

After the development of the assembly line by Henry Ford in 1913, it became even easier to manufacture modular homes at a price that was affordable to many more consumers.

And after World War II, when the soldiers returned home and started families, modular construction offered quick, low-cost housing. In the 1960s, consumers demanded more modern-looking modular buildings with complex structures and amenities.

21ST CENTURY AND BEYOND

Modular buildings have a smaller ecological footprint and can be built with durability and unique character. New technology, like better construction cranes, have allowed modular buildings to be built bigger, taller, and in many designs.

TYPES OF MODULAR CONSTRUCTION

PERMANENT MODULAR CONSTRUCTION

Permanent Modular Construction is an innovative, sustainable construction delivery approach that prefabricates single or multi-story buildings in deliverable module pieces using offsite manufacturing techniques.

These modules can be utilized as site-built projects or as a turn-key solution, and they are delivered with MEP, fixtures and interior finishes in less time, with less waste, and with better quality control than site-built projects.

RELOCATABLE BUILDINGS

A Relocatable Building is a partially or completely assembled building that complies with codes and regulations and is constructed in a building manufacturing facility using a modular construction process.

Buildings that are relocatable are designed to be reused or repurposed multiple times and transferred to new construction locations. They are used for schools, construction site offices, medical clinics, sales centers, and any other application where a movable structure may suit a temporary space requirement. These structures provide quick delivery, simple movement, minimal costs and a great deal of flexibility.

MANUFACTURING PROCESS OF MODULAR CONSTRUCTION __

Design

Every construction needs an architectural design. The first step for modular construction is similar. The designer takes into context the following:

- What the client wants; number of rooms, number of floors, floor design, kitchen design, etc.
- Environment and climatic conditions of the site to determine how many floors can be erected and what material and method should be used to tackle harsh weathers.
- The budget of the client.

ENGINEERING REVIEWS AND PERMITS

After the designs have been finalized, they go to the engineering department for a review of the standards of safety and performance. A construction or major renovation of any building requires permits from the state jurisdiction.

SITE DEVELOPMENT

The site is developed for the installation of modules. Firstly, the site is surveyed for contours of the land. Secondly, the land is excavated and graded to a level for the foundation. Then the drainage for the site is laid down.

MODULE DEVELOPMENT

The fabrication of the module begins with a welded steel frame loaded onto the assembly line. The base floors, walls and ceilings are then fabricated on the frame and the electrical and plumbing services are added. Then the interior finishing, including painting and flooring, is completed while the windows and doors are attached. The module is prepared for transportation after the exterior finish is completed.

TRANSPORTATION OF MODULES

After finishing the module fabrication, the modules are transported to the site for installation. The modules are transported by road on trailers or tow trucks.

INSTALLATION

After the modules have been transported to the site of construction, they are set in place to fix the panels and joints. For a permanent or grade foundation, the modules are supposed to be put in place by a crane. Finally, installation of the utility and electrical services is completed. [4]

ADVANTAGES

- Less material wastage can be achieved while constructing modules in a factory-controlled setting. Waste is eliminated by recycling materials, controlling inventory and protecting building materials.
- Modular structure is substantially completed in a factory using dry materials, the potential for high levels of moisture being trapped in the new construction is eliminated and thus the air quality is improved.
- Construction of modular buildings can occur simultaneously with the site and foundation work; projects can be completed 30% to 50% sooner than traditional construction.
- The removal of roughly 75% of the building construction activities from the site location decreases site disruption, vehicular traffic, and overall safety and security. Accidents and related liabilities for workers are also reduced in an indoor construction setting.
- 60 - 80% of the construction is completed inside a factory, which mitigates the risk of weather delays. Buildings are occupied sooner, creating a faster return on investment.
- Modular buildings are built to meet or exceed the same building codes and standards as site-built structures, and the same architect-specified materials used in conventionally constructed buildings are used in modular construction projects – wood, concrete and steel.
- Modular construction relies on advanced BIM for visualization to assess the energy performance and identify the most cost-effective efficiency measures. Modular construction is ideal for the use of this technology where the construction process is a collaboration of systems, materials and people like the software itself.
- Modular building provide flexibility in design, including creating high rises buildings.

DISADVANTAGES

- The modules are transported to the construction site by trucks or other forms of transportation. This in turn limits the maximum size of the modules that can be used in a structure.
- The distance of the factory from the site dictates the price of transportation. This may outweigh the cost difference between modular and conventional construction.
- A massive amount of initial capital is required to set up appropriate machinery to run a modular manufacturing plant. Also, the lack of availability of knowledgeable and experienced designers and engineers who have enough experience for modular systems is a limitation.
- The slightest change in the design, such as an electric outlets placement is not possible after the construction phase. Making these changes after the module leaves the factory compromises the structural integrity of the structure and affects the durability.
- It requires extensive planning and engineering prior to the start of the project. Additionally, because of the intricacy of module design, more thought and preparation are required when incorporating diverse components within a module, as well as when modules are lifted, transported to the final project site, set on the foundation, and linked to form the building. [5]

CASE STUDY

Six distinct innovative technologies were selected from 54 global technologies for the construction of six Light House Projects (LHPs) of about 1,000 houses each with allied infrastructure at Indore, Rajkot, Chennai, Ranchi, Agartala and Lucknow. Projects in Chennai, Tamil Nadu and Ranchi Jharkhand are prime examples of Precast Concrete Construction System in India.

Location	DUs (Storeys)	Technology	Construction Agency
1. Chennai, Tamil Nadu	1,152 (G+5)	Precast Concrete Construction System – Precast Components Assembled at Site	M/s B. G. Shirke Construction Technology Pvt. Ltd.
2. Ranchi, Jharkhand	1,008 (G+8)	Precast Concrete Construction System – 3D Volumetric	M/s SGC Magicrete LLP

Case Study I: Light House Project at Chennai, Tamil Nadu

Location of Project	Nukkampal Road, Chennai, Tamil Nadu
Plot area	29,222 sq.mt.
No. of DUs	1,152 (G+5)
Carpet area of each DU	26.78 sq.mt.
Total built up area	43439.76 sq.mt.
Technology being used	Precast Concrete Construction System - 3S System
Broad Specifications	Foundation-RCC isolated footing Structural Frame- RCC precast beam/columns Walling- AAC Blocks Floor Slabs/Roofing- RCC precast slab

- 3S system incorporates precast dense reinforced cement concrete hollow core columns, structural RCC shear walls, T/L/Rectangular shaped beams, stairs, floor/roof solid Precast RCC slabs, lintels, parapets and chajjas.
- AAC blocks are used for partition walls. The thermal and acoustic insulation provided by the AAC block masonry, facilitates reduction in energy towards maintaining comfort level temperature within enclosed habitat space. [6]
- 3S Prefab Technology completely eliminates the use of timber and forest produce of any category and the use of flyash enhances the sustainability.

Case Study II: Light House Project at Ranchi, Jharkhand

Location of Project	Dhurva, Ranchi, Jharkhand
Plot area	21,569 sq.mt.
No. of DUs	1,008 (G+8)
Carpet area of each DU	30.27 sq.mt.
Total built up area	47,860 sq.mt.
Technology being used	Precast Concrete Construction - 3D Volumetric
Broad Specifications	Structural Frame-3D Volumetric Module Walling-RCC wall Floor Slabs/Roofing-Prestressed RCC slab

Manufacturing process of the building modules

- 3D Steel moulds are created as suiting to various sizes of building units.
- High strength steel as per the structural design is placed inside 3D moulds and electrical and plumbing lines are set up. Block outs for doors and windows are also set up at the same time.

- The modules are cast into their final shape using high-performance concrete.
- Stringent quality checks are taken for each module before they are packed for shipping. [7]

Inferences

- The buildings with alternate systems may cost 10-15% higher initially but will be less by couple of times over the entire life of the building. During the life span of a building, the financial payback may exceed the additional initial cost of using alternate systems several times.
- Broader benefits, such as reductions in greenhouse gases (GHGs) and other pollutants have large positive impacts on surrounding communities and on the planet.
- Modular construction includes measures to reduce energy consumption, i.e., the embodied energy required to extract, process, transport and install building materials and the operating energy to provide services such as heating and power for equipment.

CONCLUSION

Modular construction continues to become a more popular option for many because of its advantages such as low material wastage, easy manufacturing process and shorter construction period. This form of alternative construction techniques is greener as compared to conventional construction techniques as it uses recycled material and does not pollute the air. Modular building can also use BMI technology to calculate its energy efficiency and cost effectiveness.

It is being successfully constructed in India under the Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, as shown in the case study for group housing that are nine storey high. However, there are still some limitations to it, particularly with the initial cost of construction and constraints in the size, designing and transportation of the module. Due to this reason and the disadvantages discussed in this paper, modular construction is yet to be widely used in India.

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